

Operationalizing Incomplete Historical Data: Making Reconstruction-Era Tax Records Useful, Accessible, and Comprehensible

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Abstract—Incomplete historical data can provide unique challenges to data analysis. However, it is crucial to explore this data for the information it can provide. In this project, personal property tax records from 1867 Virginia are operationalized. The data is cleaned, modeled appropriately, and made publicly accessible with a Flask web application. The project is made scalable by storing the data in a cloud database and writing query and visualization functions that can adapt to new data features. The data is demonstrated to be useful and informative despite its sparse nature. This is partially done with methods that show how incomplete historical data can be leveraged in the broader context of exploratory analysis, and partially done by making the data explorable for the public, showing that the data can also be useful for individuals and historians.

Index Terms—historical data, Mongo, Flask, visualization, sparse data, genealogy

I. INTRODUCTION

As technology advances, historical records are digitized at an increasing rate. Digital access to historical data has allowed companies like Ancestry.com to provide genealogy information to the public. Ancestry manages 10 Terabytes of data on more than 13 billion historical profiles [1]. One Shared Story (OSS), a Virginia nonprofit, builds on this work. In typical historical data, women and people of color are poorly recorded and sometimes altogether excluded. Before the American Civil War, black people in Virginia were enslaved and viewed as property, which excluded them from typical records like census data. This means that black families today have less capability to locate their own family records compared to white families. OSS works to digitize tax records, birth records, and other historical documents from Virginia that can fill this gap in the currently available data.

Data for this project is newly-digitized personal property tax data from five Virginia counties in 1867. OSS' goal is that this data be accessible to the public and searchable, so that historians can study the data and families can locate their ancestors. In addition, OSS is currently transcribing more data that can be added to the database. The data itself poses a challenge; it is sparsely populated, and its context and features are difficult to interpret.

The contribution of this project is two-fold: first, a database for data storage and a web application for accessing and searching the data must be built. This component of the project addresses OSS' practical goals. Second, the data must be explored and summarized to show what meaning can be extracted from it. This component situates this project in the broader context of Data Science. Ultimately, this project demonstrates the operationalizability of incomplete historical data through preprocessing, exploration, and user-friendly presentation while working within a scalable pipeline for the client's data storage and retrieval.

II. RELATED WORK

Genealogy data can be searched and represented in various ways. Ancestry.com [2], the industry standard for genealogical records, allows users to search for individuals by name, location, and relationship to the user. Results are displayed as individual names along with other pertinent information, like an individual's parents' names, birth date and date of death, and their residence.

The difficulty of statistical analysis for incomplete historical data is widely acknowledged. Data from the incomplete historical record is challenging for social network analysis [3] and semantic extraction [4]. In the case of historical data, missing values are often reflective of either the data collection method or the time period during which it was reflected, both challenging attempts to explore the data and representing meaning themselves [5].

In this case, an attempt to standardize and model historical data has been previously made. This attempt was made by On These Grounds, [6] (OTG) which is a joint project conducted by several universities to evaluate, describe and make accessible information regarding individuals who were enslaved in places of higher education. OTG has developed and introduced a data model for historical event data called the OTG Descriptive Model. This data model organizes information relating to a historical occurrence into four main categories: Event, Person, Organization and Place. The design of the data model created for OSS' data is heavily influenced by OTG's Descriptive Model.

III. DATA DESCRIPTION

The data is composed of 12,363 observations and 64 features. All observations have at least one missing value, denoted by a '0' when the missing feature is numeric and an empty string when the missing feature is non-numeric. These placeholders were added during data cleaning. The raw data also includes unique values that share the same information, like 'Louisa' and 'Louisa,' where the values are different because of an extra space in the string. In addition, the data includes some string values like '####' in numeric features. These issues were also addressed during data cleaning.

This personal property tax data from 1867 comes from Buckingham, Fluvanna, Louisa, Cumberland, and Orange Counties, which are located in Central Virginia. This was a tumultuous time in history, as black men and women had been recently emancipated from slavery and for the first time were largely recorded as people rather than property. It is reasonable to expect that the effects of slavery would show huge disparities between wealth by race; however, the data does not have a clear feature representing race. In addition, it was customary for enslaved people to be given their enslaver's last name. After emancipation, many freedmen and women changed their surnames as an exercise of freedom [7]. However, in Virginia some former enslaved people remained on the same plantation where they had been enslaved and worked for their previous enslaver [8]. The data contains the surnames of employees and employers, as well as several features that give clues pertaining to race of the individuals. This contextual information can be leveraged to extract meaning.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Preprocessing

1) *Cleaning*: Because the raw data included dirty data, each feature was viewed with the Python Pandas 'value_counts()' method in order to check for duplicate values. Where found, duplicate values were corrected. In addition, when erroneous values like strings in numeric features were located, these were removed. Finally, null values were replaced with either 0 or an empty string depending on the datatype of the feature.

2) *Modeling*: To better communicate the information that each feature contains, a convention for renaming the features was developed in conjunction with OSS. In this project, this is known as the 'data model.' It is built on the concept of tags.

A tag indicates an attribute referenced by a feature. The attributes were defined by OSS, and were developed to honor the attributes used by OTG in its data model. The most prominent attributes referenced in the project data model are 'Person,' 'Event,' 'Date,' 'Source,' 'Loc,' 'Count,' 'Name,' and 'Value.' These are also the tags seen most frequently.

Functionally, tags are assigned based on whether a feature contains information pertaining to that attribute. If a feature pertains to a person, that feature has the tag 'Person' in its name. A feature can have multiple tags in its name if the information refers to multiple attributes. Through the implementation of the data model, the features were given new

names like 'PersonGivenNames' and 'PersonTaxValueAggregatePersonlProperty.' As more data is added in the future, this data model will provide an example of feature definition. To document the data model, a data dictionary was created to record further detailed information on each feature.

3) *Database Creation*: The cleaned and modeled data were then moved to MongoDB, a cloud unstructured database system, for storage. Unstructured database systems have high flexibility and scalability, which permits OSS to later expand the database with new data containing new features.

B. Exploration

The second portion of the project entailed extracting meaning from the data. Given its historical context and its high frequency of missing data, capability for prediction was fairly limited. However, semi-supervised clustering, conducted by choosing the desired clusters, working backwards to check whether the clustering was appropriate, and determining significant differences between clusters based on visual comparison, was used to explore the data that was present.

1) *Race Proxy*: The feature 'PersonEventRole' was identified as a potential differentiating feature when it came to race, as the feature is not present on images of the data source, but was not explicitly defined by the client. This feature had no missing values, and classified observations as either 'taxpayer' or 'resident and taxpayer.' Semi-supervised clustering was performed, comparing measures of wealth between the two roles.

The data contains four features specifying race. The features 'PersonTaxCountNMalesOver16' and 'PersonTaxCountWMalesOver16' contain the counts of black and white males over sixteen years of age reported for each taxpayer. The features 'PersonsTaxedCountNMalesOver21' and 'PersonsTaxedCountWMalesOver21' contain the counts of black and white males over twenty-one years of age reported. These last two features are defined by the client as the 'tax record count of males [of that race] 21 years and older covered by this payment.' One of these two features is generally populated with at least a count of one, and in this project is assumed to represent the race of the taxpayer themselves. Semi-supervised clustering was performed with these features as well to see whether the two roles exhibit differences with regard to these race-related variables.

2) *Former Enslavement Status*: Once a proxy for race was developed, further clustering was performed by dividing the 'resident and taxpayer' cluster into two. A dummy variable called 'FormerlyEnslaved' was created within the web application that contains the string 'confirmed' if an individual's surname matches their employer's surname, and the string 'unconfirmed' if this is not the case. Then semi-supervised clustering was conducted, comparing wealth across all three clusters to determine whether clustering by name was a meaningful adjustment.

C. Presentation

To make the data accessible and searchable per OSS' request, a web application was made with the Python package

Flask. The application also highlights the data processing and analysis that was conducted. The user view and functionality of the application are discussed in the following Results section, but the underlying functions will be discussed here.

A search function was created for the database searching page in the web application. Per the client’s specifications, the search function takes a user-specified given name, surname, date range, and location, as well as a list of columns the user wishes to view. The function then generates and sends an appropriate query to the MongoDB database and returns a table containing the resulting data. Each user input is then compared with all features that contain relevant information. For example, a user input for location must be compared to all features that contain information about record location. To do this, the input is compared with all features whose names include the tag ‘Loc.’ In this way, the data model developed with OSS is used to access appropriate features given user inputs. See Figure 1 for the function schema. The function

Fig. 1. Search Function

for generating visualization with various combinations of user inputs was also created. Because users may select different visualization types, features, and aggregation functions, the function checks for validity of the combination of user inputs before generating the function to avoid unexpected errors. See Figure 2 for a breakdown of checking a user’s input.

Fig. 2. Graph Function

V. RESULTS

A. Exploration

After performing the first semi-supervised clustering, Figure 3 was created, representing total tax value compared across roles and grouped by county. Clearly, the ‘taxpayer’ role generally holds more wealth than the ‘resident and taxpayer’ role, and this clustering is appropriate.

Fig. 3. Tax Value Across Role and County

Fig. 4. Count of Black Males Reported by Role and County

Figure 4 shows the count of black males over 21 reported by role and grouped by county. Figure 5 shows the count of white males over 21 reported by role and grouped by county. It is clear that the role ‘resident and taxpayer’ almost exclusively reports on black males, and the role ‘taxpayer’ almost exclusively reports on white males. It is also worth noting that some black males are reported by individuals with the role of ‘taxpayer,’ and investigation of the source documents indicate that a few of these records may be transcriber errors. However, some do not appear to be errors, indicating that the black males reported by ‘taxpayer’ individuals may still have been considered property of their enslavers. There is a clear difference in race and in wealth between these clusters, indicating that ‘taxpayer’ represents white individuals and ‘resident and taxpayer’ represents black individuals.

Figure 6 shows the hierarchical structure developed after

Fig. 5. Count of White Males Reported by Role and County

Mongo database, and a functional Flask web application was written to access the data. The application permits a user to search for particular inputs and visually represent features of their choosing.

The final product is scalable, with a well-defined data model and query that is adaptable to new record types which follow the data model. It permits OSS to scale the pipeline to meet its needs. In the future, the framework developed in this project can be replicated with other sparsely populated historical data, both in extracting meaning and in making the data searchable and available to the public.

The metadata for this project can be found at the following link:

https://github.com/Data-ScienceHub/Tax

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REFERENCES

- [1] “Company Facts — Ancestry Corporate.” Ancestry Corporate. <https://www.ancestry.com/corporate/about-ancestry/company-facts>. (accessed April 30, 2023).
- [2] “Ancestry — Family Tree, Genealogy & Family History Records.” Ancestry Corporate. <https://www.ancestry.com>. (accessed April 30, 2023).
- [3] Wetherell, C. (1998). Historical Social Network Analysis. *International Review of Social History*, 43(S6), 125-144.
- [4] S. Migliorini & P. Grossi (2010). Towards the Extraction of Semantics from Incomplete Archaeological Records. Conference paper, First Online: 16 September 2017.
- [5] Steve Heitkamp. “Data as Incomplete History.” Towards Data Science. <https://towardsdatascience.com/data-as-incomplete-history-5110e3bba62b>. (accessed April 30, 2023).
- [6] “Descriptive Model · On These Grounds.” On These Grounds, <https://onthesegrounds.org/s/OTG/page/descriptive-model>. (accessed April 26, 2023).
- [7] “Changing Names.” Facing History Ourselves. <https://www.facinghistory.org/resource-library/changing-names> (accessed April 30, 2023).
- [8] “After Slavery: Race, Labor, and Politics in the Post-Emancipation Carolinas.” LDHI. https://ldhi.library.cofc.edu/exhibits/show/after_slavery/introduction--a-critical-perio/varied_experience_of_emancipat (accessed April 30, 2023).

APPENDIX

Enter Your Search Terms:

First Name
John

Last Name
Adams

County Name
Cumberland

Year Range
1867

Choose columns to display:

- SourceLocCreatedCounty
- SourceAuthorName
- EventLocJurisdictionCounty
- EventDateYear
- EventTransactionNotes
- PersonNameAlternate
- PersonNameSuffix
- PersonRole
- PersonsTaxesCountWMAlesover21
- PersonsTaxesCountWMAlesover21
- PersonRoleLocSurnameEmployer
- PersonRoleGivenNamesEmployer

Search

Selected Values:

Given Name: John
Surname: Adams
Date Range: 1867, None
Location: Cumberland
Selected Columns to Display: [EventTitle, 'PersonSurname', 'PersonGivenNames', 'PersonEventRole']

EventTitle	PersonSurname	PersonGivenNames	PersonEventRole
Personal Property Tax Recorded	Adams	John S.	taxpayer
Personal Property Tax Recorded	Bradatt	John A.	creditor and taxpayer

Fig. 11. Web Application Search Page Input and Output

X-Value:
PersonNameAlternate

Y-Value:
EventLocJurisdictionCounty

Group:
SourceType

Aggregation function:
 mean
 median
 count

Figure type:
 Table
 Bar Chart
 Scatterplot

Make graph

X-Value:
SourceLocCreatedCounty

Y-Value:
PersonsTaxesCountWMAlesover21

Group:
PersonEventRole

Aggregation function:
 mean
 median
 count

Figure type:
 Table
 Bar Chart
 Scatterplot

Make graph

Please specify a numeric x-value variable, not a categorical one.

Selected Values:

X-Value: SourceLocCreatedCounty
Y-Value: PersonsTaxesCountWMAlesover21
Grouped by: PersonEventRole
Aggregate: count
Figure type: Bar

SourceLocCreatedCounty	PersonEventRole	Count
Cumberland	creditor and taxpayer	~100
	taxpayer	~100
Bradatt	creditor and taxpayer	~100
	taxpayer	~100
Persons	creditor and taxpayer	~100
	taxpayer	~100
Other	creditor and taxpayer	~100
	taxpayer	~100

Fig. 12. Web Application Graph Page Input and Output